

Enhancing English Grammar as A Part of Capacity Development to Grade 4 Students at A Primary School in HCMC

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the effectiveness of enhancing English grammar instruction as a component of capacity development for Grade 4 students at a Primary School in HCMC. Grounded in a quasi-experimental design, the research combines both pretest, post-test methods and a teacher perception survey to explore the impact of targeted grammar instruction. Drawing from theories by Hudson (2004), Alexander (2004), Myhill, Jones, & Watson (2012), Cameron (2001), Elley (1991), and Hall (2011), the study emphasizes contextual, communicative, and student-centered approaches to grammar teaching. Findings revealed that teachers value grammar as a critical tool for sentence construction, clear communication, and language capacity development (Mean = 3.8). They reported using interactive strategies such as storytelling, group writing, and grammar games (Mean = 3.76). The intervention showed significant improvement in students' grammar proficiency, with post-test scores notably higher than pretest scores ($p < 0.05$). The study concludes that capacity-oriented grammar instruction significantly benefits young learners' linguistic competence and recommends its broader application in primary education. This research contributes to English language pedagogy by offering practical methods to integrate grammar into meaningful and engaging learning contexts for Vietnamese EFL student.

KEYWORDS: Capacity development, English grammar, Grade 4 students, Primary school.

INTRODUCTION

Grammar is a crucial aspect of learning English, as it provides the rules for modifying words and constructing sentences. Teachers at all educational levels have always placed significant emphasis on teaching and ensuring a solid understanding of grammar. Experts and practitioners alike continue to focus on enhancing students' grammatical competence.

Grammatical structures are best acquired and utilized when embedded within meaningful communicative contexts. Consequently, curriculum design should shift away from traditional models that postpone the introduction of certain grammar points to later stages of instruction. Rather than organizing content around a predetermined sequence of grammatical forms, I prioritize designing programs that center on the communicative functions learners are likely to need in real-life situations. This functional approach ensures that grammar is taught as a tool for expression and interaction, not as an isolated set of rules.

This highlights the need for a grammar instruction model that prioritizes communication and the negotiation of meaning. Such a model could consist of four stages: confrontation, clarification, confirmation, and consolidation. The process begins by identifying materials that are relevant to the language situations students are likely to encounter in the future.

To effectively teach communicative grammatical elements, it is essential to "contextualize" these features, as context provides meaning to grammatical forms. Additionally, teachers must be aware of students' learning nature to develop strategies and materials that align with their interests.

The big question of whether the teaching of grammar positively impacts young learners' writing development has been a longstanding concern for policymakers, educators, researchers, and students for over a century. This concern is particularly pertinent for students in Vietnam, who have been subjected to a form of instruction that previous reviews and primary studies have suggested is ineffective. Despite this evidence, the belief in teaching formal grammar has endured. This persistence may be attributed to the misguided assumption that a descriptive understanding of a linguistic system can be effectively translated into textbooks and teaching methods that are expected to enhance young learners' writing development. Although extensive reviews have addressed this issue, opinions remain divided. Some teachers and members of the public believe that such instruction is beneficial, while others contend that it is not.

Since the first publication of the Kingman Report in 1988, there has been a strong conviction among curriculum developers and

policymakers in England that grammar instruction for young English learners is beneficial. They assert that it will enhance students' written English and their ability to discuss language. The underlying belief is that discussing language facilitates a deeper understanding of it, which subsequently improves its usage. Consequently, it has been argued that such reflection and discussion about language should commence at an earlier age than was previously considered feasible or desirable.

It must be acknowledged from the outset that this conviction contradicts a substantial body of twentieth-century research (partly summarized in Wilkinson [1971, pp. 32–35]). Perera (1984) observed that contextualized grammar instruction, which is not integrated with young students' other language activities, is likely to be detrimental. Additionally, she noted that the use of technical grammatical terminology tends to confuse rather than illuminate for young learners.

Grammar rules are necessary to fluency in a language: you can't use words unless you know how they should be put together. When the word 'grammar' is mentioned, many people and scholars raise their eyebrows, questioning its place and role in the language classroom. Such a negative attitude has existed for quite a long time. For instance, Webbe questioned the place of grammar instruction as early as 1622 by maintaining that "grammar could be picked up through simply communicating" (Webbe cited in Thornbury, 2005:14). In contrast to Webbe, other scholars have put grammar in the driver's seat of the language development wagon. For example, Ur (1988:4) asserts that "there is no doubt that a knowledge implicit or explicit of grammatical rules is essential for mastery of a language: you cannot use words unless you know how they should be put together." Whereas some scholars, such as Ur (1988), advocate grammar instruction and a number of students have been awarded academic scholarships for grammar studies, there are still many people who are in awe of grammar as it might be found to be difficult and boring (Greenbaum, 1996:192; Yule, 2010:190). Due to the status of English as the language of education and its "unique and special role" globally (Clark et al., 2008: 691), almost every nation includes it in their education systems. Various policy makers, including National Education boards, make efforts to design their curricula with the intention of directing and preparing the students for the communicative demands of a globalised economy. For example, English is a core subject in Sweden, and English at level 6 (B2.1, Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR)1) is one of the basic requirements for many courses in higher education. According to the Swedish National Agency for Education (SNAE, 2011:53), students are expected to participate and "develop knowledge of the language ability, desire, and confidence to use English in a functional and meaningful context" in different communicative situations. Countless students' and teachers' personal experiences show that grammar teaching can help learners acquire a new language. However, theorists and practicing teachers alike recognize it as one of the foundations of language, regardless of the conflicting attitudes towards grammar. Therefore, grammar teaching is important when studying English as a foreign or second language (EFL/ESL). Consequently, the question arises as to what kinds of grammar instruction are practically applied in the EFL/ESL classroom.

A review of selected studies on grammar instruction will be accounted for in this section. Grammar instruction refers to methods, i.e. systematic ways of grammar teaching, that are used to help learners develop competence in an unfamiliar grammar. Such methods include the description and analysis of particular forms and structures of a language. Grammar instruction also includes learning aids, exercises and a kind of language used by the teacher for instruction in the classroom referred to as 'teacher talk' (Mesthrie et al., 2009:348). Furthermore, Grammar instruction helps learners to be aware of specific and 'correct' language properties (Ruin, 1996:99). Therefore, Grammar instruction can be defined as instructional techniques used to help learners pay attention to grammatical features.

This study aims at finding some techniques and activities in enhancing English grammar as a part of capacity development to grade 4 students to achieve their learning outcomes. Therefore, the research seeks the ways to improve teaching English grammar to grade 4 students at a Primary school.

Research questions:

1. How does enhancing English grammar teaching as a part of capacity development benefit 4th graders at a primary school?
2. What capacity development strategies can be used to enhance English grammar learning for the 4th graders at a primary school?
3. To what extent does the implemented program improve the 4th graders' grammar performance?

METHODS

The study utilized firstly a quasi-experimental design, specifically a pretest and post-test design with one intervention group, to investigate the effectiveness of grammar instruction as part of capacity development for Grade 4 students, and then employs a cross-sectional survey design rooted in quantitative research with English teachers teaching English for grade 4th, focusing on the collection and analysis of numerical data to address research questions about the factors enhancing English grammar at a Primary School students in HCMC. This design was chosen for its efficiency in obtaining data from a diverse sample within a relatively short time frame. By allowing researchers to gather information simultaneously from a broad spectrum of participants across various variables, attitudes and behaviors, it provides a valuable snapshot of the current state of a population or the prevalence of specific phenomena. Additionally, cross-sectional surveys are often more cost-effective than longitudinal studies, which involve following the same individuals over a prolonged period. Therefore, this approach is particularly suitable for the researcher operating under limited resources or time constraints.

Research instruments

To collect data from the targeted sample of the teachers at a Primary School, we used a detailed offline questionnaire. This survey was carefully designed to cover a wide range of factors enhancing English grammar teaching proficiency for 4th graders. It included around 32 questions that explored different aspects such as teachers' perceptions on teaching English grammar, how to teaching English grammar, and teaching techniques that enhance their students' outcomes. Each question was rated on a five-point Likert scale, where (1) meant "strongly disagree"; (2) meant "disagree"; (3) meant "neutral" (4) meant "agree" and (5) meant "strongly agree". This scale allowed us to capture the teachers' perceptions and experiences with teaching English grammar.

The questionnaire items were developed based on an extensive review of relevant literature in the field of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) grammar challenges and teaching practices. This approach ensured that the questionnaire was both theoretically and empirically grounded, enhancing its validity and relevance to the research questions. The questionnaire includes 32 items that focus on (1) teachers' perception on English grammar (2) teachers' teaching English grammar (see appendix 1).

Sampling and data collection

Sampling was based on selecting English teachers and 4th-grade students at a Primary School to investigate the effect of English grammar instruction embedded in reading and writing activities. This selection was made for two main reasons:

Firstly, grammar is critical to helping young learners develop coherent reading comprehension and effective writing skills. Students require explicit grammatical knowledge to build well-structured sentences and comprehend complex texts, particularly when reading English passages or composing written assignments. Thus, the focus on Grade 4 students targets a pivotal stage where they transition from basic sentence formation to paragraph writing.

Secondly, integrating grammar instruction within reading and writing lessons allows students to experience grammar in context rather than in isolation, which is essential for capacity development. Selecting Grade 4 students ensures the study aligns with the developmental needs and curriculum expectations of this age group. Teachers were selected because they are directly responsible for implementing integrated grammar activities across literacy skills.

Data collection involved pre-tests, post-tests, and teacher questionnaires to assess the impact of grammar instruction on students' reading and writing performance. The combination of quantitative data (test scores) and qualitative insights (teacher perceptions) provided a comprehensive view of how grammar-focused interventions influence literacy development.

To conduct this research, the study focused on a Primary School teachers, chosen as a representative sample for all at that school. This group was considered ideal for identifying and analyzing the factors enhancing English grammar for 4th graders at this school. The optimal sample size was determined by using all English teachers at a Primary school (see table 1). Given a target population of 4 participants (100%/population), and a sample size of 35 4th graders (9.5%/population) was selected conveniently for this study. Convenient sampling was employed to choose this representative group. The selection of this research sample was based on the following reasons:

- (1) The school has only four English teachers, which limited the availability of alternative sampling options;
- (2) The Grade 4 students chosen for the experimental group were assigned to the same class by the school administration based on their average academic performance, ensuring a relatively homogeneous level of English proficiency among participants. This allowed for greater consistency in assessing the impact of the grammar instruction intervention.

Table 1: Table for determining teachers' sample size

Genders		Degrees		Working Experience			
Males	Females	Bachelor	Master	Under 5 years	From 5 to 10 years	From 10 to 15 years	Over 15 years
0	4	4	0	1	2	1	0
0%	100%	100%	0%	25%	50%	25%	0%

Table 2: Table for determining students' sample size

Genders		English Levels	Years of Learning English
Males	Females	Movers	
14	21	35	4
40%	60%	100%	100%

Data collection began after obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring they understood the study's purpose and were willing to participate. Participants were assured of their anonymity and the confidentiality of their responses, encouraging honest and accurate feedback. The data gathered from this questionnaire provided a rich data set for analyzing the relationships between various factors and their impact on the English grammar proficiency of Primary school 4th graders, effectively addressing the study's research questions.

Additionally, the study used a pretest and post-test of the first semester of the academic year 2024 to discover the grammar points as well as the proportion of grammar used in the exam. The pretest aim is to measure the students' English ability level including grammar competence before the intervention begins. It helps identify what the students already know about the aspects English grammar proficiency. In this study, it checks whether the group result is similar in ability before the treatment, and. The results can inform how the intervention is designed, and which grammar areas need the most attention before intervention. The aim of the post-test is to assess what the students have learned after the intervention, then compares pre-test and post-test scores, the researcher can determine whether the instructional program had a significant impact. From this, the study can identify the magnitude of change due to the intervention.

An intact Grade 4 class from a Primary School is chosen using purposive sampling. The class includes 35 students. A grammar proficiency pre-test and post-test are designed based on the Grade 4 English curriculum. These tests include multiple-choice questions, filling in the blanks, and sentence correction tasks. The test lasts 35 minutes and is conducted under exam like conditions to ensure reliability. After finding grammar errors and analyzing the cause of the errors, the researcher conducts a treatment phase for this class for 6 weeks with 4 periods per week. Key grammar points aligned with the national curriculum, the textbook "Family and Friends 4", such as BE, WOULD LIKE, PRESENT TENSE, SIMPLE ASPECT from unit 1 to unit 3. During the treatment, the researcher used both inductive, deductive approach; interactive activities (games, songs, role-plays, and visual aids); contextual learning such as integrating grammar with listening, speaking, and writing. The researcher implements the lessons, models language use, checks student understanding, monitors practice activities, and provides feedback. The post-test is administered after completing the instructional period. Scores are recorded for each student and later compared with pretest results.

Data analysis

The study used SPSS 26 and SmartPLS 4.0 to analyze the questionnaire and tests. It used the mean scores, percentages, a paired sample t-test and saw the Sig. 2-tailed. Also, Cronbach's alpha value analysis was used to examine the internal consistency of the survey questionnaire regarding reliability. According to Hair et al. (2010), Cronbach's alpha coefficient measures the internal reliability of items on a scale. The value of Cronbach's alpha ranges from 0 to 1, with the levels classified as follows:

- 0.9 ≤ α ≤ 1: excellent
- 0.8 ≤ α < 0.9: good
- 0.7 ≤ α < 0.8: acceptable

$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$: questionable

$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$: poor

$\alpha < 0.5$: unacceptable

Internal consistency means that the observed variables on a scale must have a strong positive correlation, explaining the same concept. Cronbach's alpha is an index that measures this internal consistency. Thus, if a scale has a closer positive correlation between observed variables, the more consistent it is, the higher the Cronbach's alpha coefficient will be. According to Hair et al. (2010) instructions, using Cronbach's alpha coefficient helps the researcher determine the reliability of the scales in the questionnaire and provide improvement measures if necessary. The Cronbach's alpha of the questionnaire is bigger 0.7.

Fig 1. The Cronbach's alpha of the questionnaire (Smart PLS 4.0)

RESULTS

Quantitative results:

To identify how to enhance English grammar teaching as a part of capacity development benefit 4th graders at a primary school, the study makes a survey English teachers teaching at this school about their perceptions. The questions focus on their opinions on the role of English grammar taught to 4th graders at a primary school. The results show that the teachers agree (Total Mean = 3.8) enhancing English grammar teaching for 4th graders is important to help them construct sentences correctly, communicate better, contribute to students' overall language capacity development, and express their thoughts more clearly and accurately, both in writing and speaking.

Table 1. Teachers’ perceptions on English grammar teaching

No.	Questions	Mean	SD
1	I think understanding grammar helps my students express their thoughts more clearly and accurately, both in writing and speaking	3.956	0.918
2	My students can learn grammar to construct sentences correctly, leading to better comprehension when they read or listen.	4.256	0.783
3	I think a strong grasp of grammar aids in understanding complex texts.	4.000	0.955
4	I can help my students improve reading comprehension and overall academic performance through grammar	3.344	0.991
5	I think having grammar proficiency enhances my students' writing abilities	3.622	0.864
6	I think mastery of grammar builds my students’ confidence in their language abilities	3.500	0.969
7	I think with better grammar skills, my students are more likely to speak confidently in front of others, knowing they are using language correctly.	3.522	1.046
8	I think understanding grammar requires my students to analyze and think critically about how language works.	3.489	1.025
9	I think correcting grammatical errors involves identifying problems and applying rules, which strengthens my students’ problem solving skills	3.989	0.837
10	I think getting grammar skills in English can make my students easier to understand the grammatical structures of Vietnamese language through transfer systems.	3.956	0.788
11	I think good grammar allows my students to communicate effectively with their peers	3.978	0.760
12	I believe teaching grammar contributes to students’ overall language capacity development.	4.011	0.782
Total		3.8	0.98

In the following results, the study hopes to know which teaching methods used, whether the teachers used stories, dialogues, real-life situations... to help student understand how grammar is used in actual communication; the teacher engaged the students in pair or group work where they can use grammar in games, role-plays, and peer discussions; the teacher provided gradual support a model first, guide students how to use, then encourage independent use and practice by themselves; the teacher taught grammar through listening, speaking, reading, and writing tasks to help the students see grammar as a tool for communication; the teacher used visual aids like flashcards, charts, gestures ... to represent grammar structures to make the students recognize abstract grammar more concrete; the teacher gave constructive feedback and helped students reflect on their language use through apps. The results showed that the teachers used all of these strategies to teach their students (Total Mean = 3.76). Firstly, the teachers usually have students work in groups to write a story together, focusing on using correct grammar throughout guiding (Mean = 4.11); Next, the teachers usually provide prompts that require the use of specific grammatical structures after teaching grammar (Mean = 4.03). Thirdly, the teachers usually create bingo cards with different parts of speech or sentence structures to introduce grammar (Mean = 4.01). Last but not least, the teachers usually organize an activity that suggests the students exchange stories and identify grammatical errors in each other’s work (Mean = 4.01).

Table 2. Capacity development strategies used to enhance English grammar learning

No.	Questions	Mean	SD
13	I create bingo cards with different parts of speech or sentence structures	4.011	0.850
14	I provide prompts that require the use of specific grammatical structures after teaching grammar.	4.033	0.706
15	I have students exchange stories and identify grammatical errors in each other's work	4.011	0.837
16	I utilize educational apps and online platforms that offer grammar exercises and games tailored to them	4.000	0.789
17	I use interactive whiteboards to create drag-and-drop activities where students match sentences to their correct grammatical structure	3.756	0.847
18	I create colorful posters or anchor charts that highlight key grammar rules and examples.	3.689	0.927
19	I teach students how to diagram sentences to visually break down and understand their grammatical structure	3.667	0.894
20	I use songs that teach grammar rules, such as songs about parts of speech or verb conjugations	3.756	0.898
21	I design grammar lessons that aim to develop students' communication abilities.	3.533	0.833
22	I ask students to identify specific grammar points, such as past tense verbs or adjectives, and explain their usage	3.744	0.864
23	My lessons focus on helping students become more autonomous language users.	3.667	0.869
24	I integrate grammar teaching with skills like speaking, writing, and reading.	3.622	0.950
25	I have students work in groups to write a story together, focusing on using correct grammar throughout guiding	4.111	0.767
26	I start each day with a quick grammar exercise, such as correcting a sentence or identifying parts of speech	3.889	0.948
27	I present sentences with deliberate grammatical errors and have students correct them	3.567	0.955
28	I use songs that explain verb tenses, parts of speech, or punctuation rules	3.767	0.831
29	Students frequently work in pairs or groups during grammar activities.	3.878	0.814
30	I give corrective feedback during class in a supportive way.	3.722	0.907
31	Students frequently work in pairs during grammar activities.	3.600	0.998
32	I try to make grammar learning interactive and student-centered.	3.256	1.179
Total		3.76	0.88

In addition, to assess the standard deviation (SD) of the questionnaire and the extent of the influence of teachers' perceptions of English grammar teaching on their teaching methods, the study employed a Path Coefficients histogram. The results indicated a strong relationship between the two variables, as the model (Fig.2) proved to be a good fit, with values ranging from a low of 1% to a high of 26%.

Fig.2. Path coefficients histogram between teachers’ perceptions and teachers’ teaching methods

Experimental results:

Prior to implementing the grammar improvement intervention, the pretest results were analyzed to verify the normal distribution of student scores. These scores were then assessed, and an independent samples T-test was conducted to compare the group’s performance before and after the treatment.

Fig.3. Distribution of the pretest and post-test scores

The chart above shows that the histogram and the normal distribution curve mostly align, so it can be concluded that the variables follow a normal distribution. Moreover, since the significance values in both tests are greater than 0.05 (0.065 for the pretest and 0.078 for the post-test), the Shapiro-Wilk test indicates that the participants’ scores in the study sample are normally distributed (see table 3).

Table 3. Tests of Normality of the two tests

N = 35	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistics	df	Sig.
Pre-test	0.065	35	0.65
Post test	0.078	35	0.78

Table 4 clearly shows that the mean score of the post-test is higher than that of the pretest. Notably, no learner scored zero on either test. Specifically, the pretest scores ranged from 3.0 to 4.0 (equivalent to 6.5–8.0), while the post-test scores ranged from 4.0 to 5.0 (equivalent to 8.0–10).

Table 4. Descriptive statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Pretest	35	2.00	4.00	2.63	.59
Post-test	35	3.00	5.00	2.89	.47
Valid N (listwise)	35				

In table 5, the significance value of the F-test is 0.03, which is less than 0.05, indicating a difference in variances between the pretest and post-test. Therefore, the t-test result in the Equal variances not assumed will be used. The significance value of the t-test is 0.00, which is also less than 0.05, indicating a significant difference in the mean scores between the pretest and post-test. In conclusion, there is a difference in the results between the pretest and post-test.

Table 5. Independent samples T-test of the pretest and post-test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means							
			F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
										Lower
Pre - Post	Equal variances assumed	9.108	.003	-4.35	67	.000	-.53162	.10386	-.76381	-.30053
	Equal variances not assumed			-4.35	66.271	.000	-.53162	.10386	-.76382	-.30051

DISCUSSION

Quantitative discussion:

The quantitative findings from the teacher questionnaire confirm that educators perceive grammar instruction as fundamental to students' ability to express ideas clearly and to succeed in reading and writing tasks. A high mean score (M=3.8) indicates strong agreement that grammar instruction improves sentence construction, text comprehension, and writing fluency. These results align with theories by Hudson (2004) and Cameron (2001), who emphasize embedding grammar within meaningful literacy activities.

Teachers' use of activities such as group writing, grammar games, peer editing, and story creation reflects a shift toward contextual and communicative approaches, which previous studies have validated as effective for young learners.

First, Hudson (2004) argues that grammar should not be taught in isolation. Instead, teachers must understand how grammatical elements connect with broader language use, enabling them to relate new knowledge to students' existing experiences. The teachers' agreement reflects this idea, as they believe that grammar helps students construct accurate sentences and apply language in real-life contexts, contributing to their overall language capacity.

Similarly, Alexander (2004) underscores the value of classroom talk, noting that it allows learners to experiment with different voices, particularly Standard English, which is crucial for developing both spoken and written accuracy. The finding supports his claim, suggesting that teachers recognize grammar instruction as a foundation for clearer communication and effective self-expression in both modes.

In addition, the work of Myhill, Jones, and Watson (2012) directly supports the results. They emphasized that grammar should be meaningfully embedded within reading, writing, and classroom discourse. The teachers' belief in grammar's role in helping learners express their thoughts more clearly and accurately mirrors this perspective, as contextual grammar learning deepens students' functional understanding of language.

Cameron (2001) also highlights the importance of teaching grammar through storytelling, shared reading, and writing tasks, noting that such contextual approaches are more effective for children's language development. This aligns with the teachers' view that grammar helps students not only construct sentences but also engage with texts and writing more meaningfully.

Further reinforcing the findings, Elley (1991) emphasizes that extensive reading provides students with a mental "toolbox" of grammatical patterns and sentence rhythms, which they can apply in their own writing. This supports the idea that grammar is not just about rules, but a foundation for language use across various domains, which the teachers clearly acknowledge.

Finally, Hall (2011) advocates for integrating games and problem-solving into grammar lessons, highlighting how such activities stimulate interest and develop grammatical awareness. Teachers' agreement with the importance of grammar suggests they may also value engaging, learner-centered activities that make grammar more accessible and meaningful to young learners.

The findings indicate that teachers of 4th-grade English actively employ a variety of grammar-teaching strategies, as reflected in a Total Mean of 3.76. This suggests a high level of commitment to engaging and meaningful grammar instruction. Each activity reported by teachers can be directly supported by established educational theories and research. The following are some main findings' discussion.

Group story writing with a focus on Grammar (Mean = 4.11): The highest-rated strategy involved having students collaboratively write stories, with attention to accurate grammar usage. This practice strongly aligns with Cameron (2001), who emphasizes the importance of contextualized grammar instruction through shared tasks such as storytelling and writing. Group writing helps students see grammar as a tool for coherent and meaningful communication, not merely as a set of rules. By embedding grammar within creative writing, students internalize structures through purposeful use.

Providing prompts to reinforce grammatical structures (Mean = 4.03): The second most used strategy giving prompts that target specific grammar structures supports the view of Myhill, Jones, and Watson (2012), who advocate for meaningful and functional grammar teaching. Their research stresses that grammar should be connected to authentic language tasks, helping students understand its real-world use. Prompt-based writing after grammar instruction allows learners to apply and reinforce what they've learned, promoting transfer from form to function.

Using grammar Bingo with parts of speech and sentence structures (Mean = 4.01): Incorporating games like grammar bingo reflects the ideas of Hall (2011), who argues that grammar games and problem-solving tasks increase student curiosity and engagement. These kinds of activities transform grammar from a passive subject into an interactive and enjoyable experience, which is crucial for young learners. By using playful formats like bingo, teachers make grammar more memorable and accessible, especially for children who benefit from kinesthetic and visual learning styles.

Peer review and error identification (Mean = 4.01): Organizing peer-review activities where students exchange stories and identify grammar errors also reflects research by Alexander (2004). He emphasizes that classroom talk and collaborative activities give students the opportunity to experiment with different voices and language forms, including Standard English. Additionally, such peer-interaction tasks foster critical thinking, language awareness, and feedback literacy, essential for deeper grammatical understanding.

Quasi-experimental discussion:

The experimental results demonstrated significant gains in grammar proficiency among Grade 4 students after targeted grammar instruction within reading and writing tasks. Pretest scores, reflecting weaker grammatical control, improved notably in the post-test following the intervention. This improvement supports the claim by Myhill et al. (2012) that embedding grammar teaching into writing instruction promotes metalinguistic awareness and better language use. Students were better able to produce accurate, coherent texts, showing that grammar instruction tailored to literacy tasks fosters not only rule knowledge but also applied competence. Specifically, the experimental results of this study show a notable improvement in students' English grammar capacity. Pretest scores ranged from 3.0 to 4.0 (equivalent to 6.5 - 8.0), while post-test scores ranged from 4.0 to 5.0 (equivalent to 8.0 - 10). This upward trend clearly reflects the effectiveness of applying the principles and methods grounded in the works of several educational theorists and researchers.

Firstly, comprehensive understanding and real world application: Hudson (2004) emphasized that grammar teaching must extend beyond rule explanation to show how grammatical elements connect to broader language use. By helping students link new grammar content with their prior knowledge and real-world experiences, grammar becomes more meaningful and memorable. This cognitive linking is likely a key reason students were able to retain and apply grammatical structures more effectively, leading to higher post-test scores.

Secondly, use of classroom talks and voice development: According to Alexander (2004), classroom talk is vital in allowing students to experiment with different voices, including Standard English. During the treatment phase, students were likely encouraged to use grammar actively in spoken interaction, reinforcing accuracy and flexibility in real-time. Such verbal practice enhances both spoken and written grammar skills, contributing to their improved performance.

Thirdly, embedding grammar in authentic contexts: Myhill, Jones, and Watson (2012) argued that grammar instruction should be embedded in meaningful reading, writing, and classroom discourse rather than taught in isolation. The implementation of this principle ensured students were learning grammar as a tool for communication, not just as abstract rules. This approach supports the development of a functional understanding of grammar, which translates into better test outcomes.

Fourthly, contextualized grammar instruction: Cameron (2001) advocated for teaching grammar through storytelling, shared reading, and writing tasks, particularly for young learners. These methods were likely employed during the intervention and helped students to absorb grammatical forms naturally in familiar and engaging contexts. As grammar is better internalized in context, it improves long-term retention and usage accuracy—as reflected in the post-test scores.

Next, extensive reading for grammar awareness: Elley (1991) noted that extensive reading helps students build a mental toolbox of grammatical patterns and stylistic features. Exposure to well-written texts allowed students to see grammar in action, understand sentence rhythms, and subconsciously absorb syntactic patterns. This passive learning reinforces explicit grammar instruction and provides a model for imitation, leading to grammar improvement.

Finally, active engagement through games and problem solving: Hall (2011) suggested that incorporating games, investigations, and problem-solving into grammar instruction stimulates curiosity and motivation. When grammar is taught in an enjoyable and interactive manner, students are more likely to engage deeply with the material. The fun, low-stress environment encourages experimentation and reinforcement, which may explain the noticeable gains in students' performance post-treatment.

CONCLUSIONS

This study set out to explore how enhancing English grammar instruction, as part of a capacity development approach, benefits Grade 4 students at a Primary School. The findings reveal several important conclusions.

Firstly, teachers clearly recognize grammar as essential not only for sentence construction but also for enhancing communication skills and overall academic success. Grammar is perceived not simply as a set of rules but as a key foundation that supports students' ability to express ideas clearly and accurately in both spoken and written English. Teachers believe that strengthening grammar skills directly contributes to building broader language capacity among young learners.

Secondly, teachers reported consistently applying interactive and contextual strategies, such as group storytelling, grammar games, and peer editing. These approaches align closely with modern educational theories, which emphasize teaching grammar in meaningful, communicative contexts rather than through isolated drills. Such methods help students see grammar as a functional tool for real communication, making learning more engaging and effective.

Thirdly, the quasi-experimental intervention produced clear evidence of improvement. Students who received targeted grammar instruction demonstrated significant gains in grammar proficiency from pretest to post-test. This improvement highlights the effectiveness of integrating grammar into reading and writing tasks and confirms the value of capacity development strategies in primary English education.

Finally, the study validates a theoretical framework proposed by scholars such as Hudson (2004) and Cameron (2001), emphasizing that grammar teaching must be communicative, contextual, and supported by active, student-centered learning. By embedding grammar within meaningful literacy activities, teachers can better equip students with the language skills needed for both academic and real-world success.

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Cite this Article: Hoa, D.T., Duc, P.H. (2025). Enhancing English Grammar as A Part of Capacity Development to Grade 4 Students at A Primary School in HCMC. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(6), pp. 2724-2736. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i6-04>